

Open Science Plan-Track-Assess Pathways

Project Management and Quality Guidelines: Handbook

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Revision History

Table 1. Document Revision History.

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Disclaimer

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Abbreviations

AE	Affiliated Entity	QAM	Quality Assurance Manager
AP	Associated Partner	TQAB	Technical and Quality Assurance Board
BEN	Beneficiary	TL	Task Leader
CA	Consortium Agreement	TM	Technical Manager
CM	Community Manager	TRM	Training Manager
DMP	Data Management Plan	WP	Work Package
DoA	Description of the Action	WPL	Work Package Leader
EAB	External Advisory Board		
ET	Exploitation Team		
FM	Financial Manager		
GA	General Assembly		
KER	Key Exploitable Result		
KPI	Key Performance Indicator		
PA	Project Administrator		
PC	Project Coordinator		
PSC	Project Steering Committee		
PM	Project Manager		
PMB	Project Management Board		

Executive Summary

This is the Project Handbook for the OSTrails project, detailing the overarching administrative, communication and quality policies, procedures, and practices for Consortium partners to refer to throughout the project's duration. Its objective is to facilitate efficient and seamless collaboration within the consortium, ensuring successful project management and delivering high-quality outcomes, as outlined in the Grant Agreement. It contains all relevant information and tools that are essential to fulfil all project management, reporting and communication tasks, and will be kept as a living document in the shared Teams to be enhanced as the project matures and new needs might arise.

Introduction

This document contains essential information for managing and executing project activities and as such it is prepared early in project's lifetime and may need to be updated within the project timeline with findings, restrictions, and results of the activity, if any. Hence, it's kept as a living document in the shared Teams point. This document serves as a guide for the project coordinator, in order to ensure that quality reviews will occur at appropriate points until the completion of the project, as well as a reference for all the project partners, in order to understand their responsibilities, regarding the project deliverables and outcomes. Moreover, this document establishes a framework for the project coordination team to effectively carrying out all management activities and monitor the project for current and future risks and, thus, act proactively and effectively. It is also a handbook for every member of the consortium to conduct their contractual project activities maintaining a high-quality output level, engaging into an efficient and effective collaboration scheme. It also presents potential risks that might threaten the smooth accomplishment of the project which will need to be monitored and handled continuously during the project, highlighting status of risks until project's end and beyond.

The OSTrails Handbook extends into three sections:

- The first section (**Project Management**) provides information about the consortium, the project's governing bodies, detailing their roles, and meeting frequencies. It also presents the communication channels to be utilised among beneficiaries (such as file sharing, teleconference options, mailing lists) and includes a toolkit containing all necessary materials and information to facilitate the production of project outcomes (including logos, templates, and file naming conventions).
- The second section (**Quality Assurance**) outlines the Quality Assurance procedures in a variety of project assets, such as deliverables, events, dissemination material, publications, to be followed to ensure the effective and efficient delivery of OSTrails project outcomes. OSTrails will employ a peer review process involving WP leaders, designated reviewers, and a final review by the Project Coordinator to maintain high-quality deliverables. Specific rules and timelines are provided to facilitate smooth revision processes for all project deliverables.
- The third section (**Risk Management**) offers a first indication of risks and suggests the paths and means to mitigate them.

The Handbook is designed to serve as an internal guide for the project's daily activities. It should be noted that this document does not hold any legal validity, and any disputes must be resolved in accordance with the Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement.

1. Project Management

In this section, the Consortium is explained along with the governing bodies (both unipersonal and collective) established for the efficient coordination and internal operation of the project are described, also covering the operational rules that guide everyday activities, and the roles and responsibilities distributed among partners. As stipulated in the Grant Agreement, the governance of OSTrails is organised into a multi-level structure to ensure:

1. The implementation of the work plan and achievement of project objectives, maintaining effective coordination among various work packages (WPs), and ensuring the timely completion of high-quality project deliverables.
2. Seamless communication and relationships among beneficiaries, affiliated entities, and associate partners, encompassing conflict resolution and the management of knowledge and intellectual property.
3. Close monitoring and compliance of both the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement with the EC, covering administrative and financial matters, as well as any legal agreements with external parties, if applicable.

1.1. Consortium

The OSTrails consortium brings together **thirty-eight partners** (twenty-six beneficiaries, ten affiliated entities and two associated partners), representing **twenty-two Research Performing Organisations (RPOs)** and the **five Science Clusters**. It builds on their technical expertise, managed services, and research communities to collectively address the limitations of the current research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem in the planning, tracking, assessing stages of research and enhance it with pragmatic fit-for-purpose solutions in different national and thematic settings.

The Consortium (

Table 2) includes partner organisations from **17 European countries** (Austria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Serbia, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom) and **14 Clusters' organisations research infrastructures** (FAIRsharing, PaNOSC, SOLEIL, ILL, JERICO, CLARIN, CESSDA, SSHOC, LIFEWATCH, ESCAPE, OEAW, TAU, KNAW, ESRF). The partners have been selected so that they are complementary and well-balanced to successfully address all research, technology, and real-world challenges of the project.

Table 2. Members of the Consortium.

N°	ROLE	SHORT NAME	LEGAL NAME	COUNTRY
1	COO	OPENAIRE AMKE	OPENAIRE AMKE	EL
1.1	AE	UNIWARSAW	UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI	PL
1.2	AE	RBI	RUDER BOSKOVIC INSTITUTE	HR
1.3	AE	SIKT	SIKT KUNNSKAPSSEKTORENS TJENESTELEVERANDOR	NO
1.4	AE	FECYT	FUNDACION ESPANOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGIA, F.S.P., FECYT	ES
1.5	AE	TU Dublin	TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY DUBLIN	IE
1.6	AE	AUTH	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	EL
1.7	AE	UBEOGRADU	UNIVERZITET U BEOGRADU	RS
2	BEN	TU WIEN	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN	AT
3	BEN	UPM	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	ES
4	BEN	CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT
5	BEN	ARC	ATHINA EREVNITIKOKENTRO KAINOTOMIAS STIS TECHNOLOGIES TIS PLIROFORIAS, TON EPIKOINONION KAI TIS GNOSIS	EL
6	BEN	CVUT	CESKE VYSOKE UCENI TECHNICKE V PRAZE	CZ
7	BEN	Codevence	CODEVENCE SOLUTIONS SRO	CZ
8	BEN	CITE	COMMUNICATION & INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES EXPERTS ANONYMOS ETAIREIA SYMVOULEFTIKON KAI ANAPTYXIAKON YPIRESION	EL
9	BEN	UMINHO	UNIVERSIDADE DO MINHO	PT
9.1	AE	FCT	FUNDACAO PARA A CIENCIA E A TECNOLOGIA	PT
10	BEN	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN - KNAW	NL

11	BEN	INRIA	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE EN INFORMATIQUE ET AUTOMATIQUE	FR
12	BEN	UNIVIE	UNIVERSITAT WIEN	AT
13	BEN	CLARIN	CLARIN ERIC	NL
13.1	AE	OEAW	OESTERREICHISCHE AKADEMIE DER WISSENSCHAFTEN	AT
14	BEN	CESSDA ERIC	CESSDA ERIC	NO
14.1	AE	TAU-FSD	TAMPEREEN KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR	FI
15	BEN	ESRF	EUROPEAN SYNCHROTRON RADIATION FACILITY	FR
16	BEN	SOLEIL	SYNCHROTRON SOLEIL SOCIETE CIVILE	FR
17	BEN	LIFEWATCH	E-SCIENCE EUROPEAN INFRASTRUCTURE FOR BIODIVERSITY AND ECOSYSTEM RESEARCH	ES
18	BEN	SOCIB	SOCIB - CONSORCIO PARA EL DISEÑO, CONSTRUCCION, EQUIPAMIENTO Y EXPLOTACION DEL SISTEMA DE OBSERVACION COSTERO DE LAS ILLES BALEARS	ES
19	BEN	FMI	ILMATIETEEN LAITOS	FI
20	BEN	OBSPARIS	OBSERVATOIRE DE PARIS	FR
21	BEN	PSNC	INSTYTUT CHEMII BIOORGANICZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	PL
22	BEN	CSC	CSC-TIETEEN TIETOTEKNIIKAN KESKUS OY	FI
23	BEN	TU GRAZ	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET GRAZ	AT
24	BEN	UGOT	GOETEBORGS UNIVERSITET	SE
25	BEN	RWTH AACHEN	RHEINISCH-WESTFAELISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE AACHEN	DE
26	BEN	SURF BV	SURF BV	NL
27	AP	UOXF	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	UK
28	AP	UESSEX	UNIVERSITY OF ESSEX	UK

1.2. Structure, Roles and Processes

OSTrails sets an ambitious workplan that requires strong expertise and organisational structure to ensure the quality and achievability of the project results while meeting diversity needs. Given that the project will leverage cutting-edge technologies alongside a diverse range of skills and approaches, fostering strong collaboration among partners is a clear prerequisite to establish a comprehensive project-wide knowledge base.

Figure 1. OSTrails Management structure.

The project management structure (**Figure 1**) outlines the distinct roles of beneficiaries and partners according to the project's work plan and the needed levels of decision-making and advisory support. The subsequent roles are distinguished between **management** and **operational** coordinating streams.

1.2.1. Individual Roles

Table 3 lists the management roles within OSTrails, and the people who perform the corresponding managerial tasks.

Table 3. Management Roles.

ROLE	BENEFICIARY	NAME
Project Coordinator (PC)	OpenAIRE	Natalia Manola

		natalia.manola@openaire.eu
Deputy Project Coordinator (DPC)	ARC	Elli Papadopoulou elli.p@athenarc.gr
Financial Manager (FM)	OpenAIRE	Mike Hatzopoulos mike@di.uoa.gr
Project Admin (PA)	OpenAIRE	Eleni Koulocheri eleni.koulocheri@openaire.eu
Project Manager (PM)	OpenAIRE	Tassos Stavropoulos tassos.stavropoulos@openaire.eu
Technical Manager	TU WIEN	Tomasz Miksa tomasz.miksa@tuwien.ac.at
Training Manager	UMINHO	Pedro Principe pedro.principe@usdb.uminho.pt
Quality Assurance Manager	CITE	Georgios Papanikos gpapanikos@cite.gr
Community Manager	CLARIN	Daan Broeder daan@clarin.eu
	LIFEWATCH	Christos Arvanitidis ceo@lifewatch.eu

Project Coordinator (PC) Role

The Project Coordinator oversees the seamless implementation of the project, ensures consistent communication between the European Commission and the consortium, and ensures that all administrative and financial reporting adheres to EC regulations and is accurately submitted to the Funding Authority. The duties of the Project Coordinator are delineated as follows:

- Organising and leading the General Assembly (GA).

- Monitoring the adherence of the Parties to their obligations outlined in the Grant and Consortium Agreements.
- Maintaining an updated and accessible contact list of consortium members and relevant individuals.
- Gathering, reviewing for consistency, and submitting reports, deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications), and requested documents to the Funding Authority.
- Disseminating project-related documents and information to concerned Parties.
- Managing the financial contribution of the Funding Authority and executing payment responsibilities.
- Providing Parties with official copies or originals of necessary documents upon request, if in the exclusive possession of the PC, for claims submission.
- Handling amendments related to the Grant Agreement.
- Organising and overseeing meetings of the Project Steering Committee (PSC).
- Collaborating with the PSC and the Technical Manager to define the overarching technical strategy guiding the project team's implementation efforts.
- Ensuring the achievement of scientific and technical objectives of the project.
- Monitoring project progress in alignment with the primary objectives outlined in the Description of Action (DoA).
- Ensuring the appropriate engagement and visibility of project members.
- Reporting on the advancement of project activities.

Deputy Project Coordinator (DPC) Role

The Deputy Project Coordinator (DPC) supports the PC in overseeing the entire research project from planning to execution in all aforementioned activities. At the same time, they serve as the scientific manager fostering collaboration and guiding WP activities to set expectations and tasks, overseeing data management processes, and ensuring that scientific research is conducted according to established protocols, methodologies, and ethical standards.

Financial Manager (FM) Role

The responsibilities of Financial Manager (FM) are as follows:

- Facilitating any required amendments to the Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement with the Funding Authority, as determined by the GA.
- Monitoring resource expenditure and initiating corrective measures at the beneficiary or consortium level, if deemed necessary.

Project Administrator (PA) Role

The Project Administrator (PA) works alongside the PC and FM concerning the day-to-day operations of the project:

- Managing communication tools, collaborative platforms, and activity management methodologies.
- Ensuring quality assurance for the project.
- Scheduling meetings and reviews.
- Preparing for audits.
- Conducting the 6-month activity and effort reporting.
- **Project Manager (PM) Role**
- The Project Manager (PM) supports the PA in all administrative activities.
- **Technical Manager (TM) Role**

The Technical Manager ensures the fulfilment of the scientific and technical goals of the project.

- Co-leading the Project Steering Committee (PSC) and setting the overarching technical strategy to guide the project team in its execution.
- Overseeing adherence to the objectives outlined in the Grant Agreement.
- Collaborating closely with the Quality Assurance Manager, especially on risk analysis and mitigation.
- Arranging strategic presentations on project progress for external stakeholders.
- Ensuring active engagement and visibility of project members.
- Collaborating closely with the PC to deliver clear and precise Technical Periodic Reports, while the PC handles the day-to-day project management responsibilities.

Training Manager (TRM) Role

The Training Manager (TRM) is responsible for meeting the training and capacity building needs of the project:

- Conducting requirement assessments for each service, identifies skill gaps within targeted user groups, and develops tailored training programs to address these gaps.
- Ensuring the effectiveness of training by monitoring performance following interventions.
- Collaborating with technical partners to draft instructional service manuals, onboarding materials, and other relevant documentation.
- Supporting pilots training events.

Quality Assurance Manager (QAM) Role

Quality Assurance Manager (QAM) ensures that all project activities maintain high quality. Their responsibilities include:

- Establishing the QA Strategy.
- Proposing and planning of QA activities.
- Coordinating the design of QA procedures for each deliverable type.
- Designing and supervising approval instruments.
- Assigning deliverable's reviewers and supervising the review processes.
- Coordinating the resolution of QA issues.

In overall, the QAM establishes and supervises project's mechanisms that guarantee the quality of its outcomes, while accommodating all the complexity and diversity of research and innovation activities of the project.

Community Manager (CM) Role

The Community Manager (CM) aims at building awareness about the project.

- Establishing the groundwork for clear communication regarding the project's concept and potential advantages to stakeholders.
- Disseminating research findings to sustain ongoing interest in the project's endeavours.
- Laying the groundwork for future collaborations among involved stakeholders,
- optimising the project's effectiveness.
- Capitalising on opportunities for utilising the project's outcomes during and beyond its development.
- Coordinating the seamless participation of science clusters in the project, as well as the engagement of their RIs.
- Organising communication and dissemination activities of the pilots and science clusters.

1.2.2. Project Steering Committee

The Project Steering Committee (PSC) serves as the executive body responsible for the overall coordination and steering of project work. It holds the authority to address daily implementation issues, allocate resources, review, and approve Periodic Reports and Deliverables, prepare project reviews, and achieve Milestones.

Table 4. Roles per institution.

ROLE	BENEFICIARY	NAME OR DEPUTY
Coordination	OpenAIRE	Natalia Manola
Technical Management	TU WIEN	Tomasz Miksa

Community Management	CLARIN LIFEWATCH	Daan Broeder Christos Arvanitidis
Training Management	UMINHO	Pedro Principe
Quality Assurance Management	CITE	Georgios Papanikos

The PSC ensures fair representation from both national and ESFRI Cluster perspectives (**Table 4**). It assigns responsibilities to organisations and individuals who have proven their success in implementing EOSC and Open Science, thereby ensuring the project's effectiveness in delivery. In addition, PSC deploys the exploitation strategy and identifies the key exploitable results (KERs) of the project.

The PSC will establish a consortium communication policy, fostering appropriate communication dynamics and incorporating the implementation of an intranet to facilitate management activities, communication, and information exchange among Participants. Concerning conflict resolution, the Project organisation is structured to support a bottom-up approach. Any conflicts among Participants within a specific activity will be addressed at the WP level with the assistance of the respective WP Leaders (WPLs). If unresolved, the matter will be elevated to the PSC, which will employ mediation and expert/referent powers to impartially seek resolution. Ultimately, the PSC may also choose to refer the matter to the GA for broader consultation.

Led by the PC (OpenAIRE) and co-led by TM (TU Wien) and the Community Coordinator (LIFEWATCH/CLARIN), the PSC consists of the WPLs and two community leads (one for the EOSC Clusters and one for the Institutions), allowing several members from each organisation leading a WP to participate (with one vote per WP). Consortium partners not serving as work package leaders may also attend PSC meetings as necessary. Appointed members of the PSC are included in **Table 5**.

Table 5. Project Steering Committee Members.

BENEFICIARY	ROLE	DELEGATES
OpenAIRE	WP6 Leader	Natalia Manola (PC); Paolo Manghi; Tassos Stavropoulos; Eleni Koulocheri; Mike Hatzopoulos
TU WIEN	WP1 Leader	Tomasz Miksa
CVUT	WP2 Leader	Marek Suchanek
UPM	WP3 Leader	Mark Wilkinson

UNIVIE	National Institutions Leader	Gerda McNeill; Daniel Spichtinger
CLARIN	WP5 Leader and EOSC Clusters Leader	Daan Broeder; Francesca Frontini
LIFEWATCH	WP4 Leader	Christos Arvanitidis
ARC	Scientific Leader	Elli Papadopoulou
UMINHO	Training Management	Pedro Principe
CITE	Quality Assurance Management	Georgios Papanikos

The PSC is responsible for:

- Overseeing and monitoring all activities within the WPs.
- Coordinating the preparation of deliverables and gathering contributions from other partner organisations involved in the respective WPs for both internal and external reports.
- Ensuring the production of deliverables of high quality and adherence to the standards outlined in the "**Quality Assurance**" section.
- Holding monthly meetings unless a higher frequency is deemed necessary.
- Actively engaging in project management as members of the PSC, aiding the PC and the TM in coordinating activities across WPs and addressing pertinent issues.
- Preparing technical and status presentations as needed.
- Making decisions on technical roadmaps concerning the DoA.
- Mediating conflicts among work packages.
- Managing risks associated with the project.
- Executing decisions made by the General Assembly (GA).
- Drafting the agenda for GA meetings.
- Assisting the PC in organising meetings with the Funding Authority and preparing relevant data and deliverables.
- Issuing press releases when deemed necessary.
- Sharing comments/results/actions along with project KPI values and Risk Assessment results in each PSC Meeting, in the chosen communication channels.

PSC meeting and Agenda preparation

The PC is tasked with convening the PSC, which is scheduled to assemble once a month or upon a written request from any PSC member and the PC. Extraordinary meetings must be communicated with a minimum of 7-day notice. The agenda for the meetings will be circulated prior to the meeting. Any SC Member has the authority to include an item on the original agenda through written notification to all other SC Members. Furthermore, items may be added to the agenda during the meeting provided there is consensus among participants.

Voting rules and quorum

For PSC deliberations and decisions to be valid, a minimum of two-thirds (2/3) of its voting members must be present or represented. Decisions will be made by striving for consensus among the Parties, and if consensus cannot be achieved, a two-thirds (2/3) majority of the votes cast will determine the outcome. In the event of a tie, the PC will have the deciding vote.

Minutes

The PC is responsible for generating written minutes for every PSC meeting, serving as the official record of all decisions made. Within 15 calendar days of the meeting, minutes draft is to be distributed to all PSC Members. If no objections are received in writing within 10 calendar days of sending, the minutes will be deemed accepted. The minutes will be shared and stored in the dedicated shared cloud folder, allowing the PC to notify Members upon completion by sending a link to the shared file. If Members don't request changes, no additional notifications will be issued.

Minutes of PSC meetings, once accepted, shall be sent by the PC to the ostrails-all@openaire.eu mailing list.

MEETING RULES

Agenda to be sent one week ahead of time

Minutes to be sent out for approval

1.2.3. General Assembly (GA)

The General Assembly (GA) serves as the highest decision-making authority within OSTrails ([Error! Reference source not found.](#)). Its primary purpose is to oversee project activities at a strategic level and to evaluate the scientific merit of the project. Comprising

one representative and one deputy from each partner the GA holds formal responsibility for ensuring the successful completion of the project and serves as the ultimate decision-making body for critical issues affecting the entire project. These issues include significant alterations to the overall strategy, decisions requiring unanimous agreement (such as changes in partnerships), and any other matters referred to it by the PSC (refer to section 1.2.2). The specific rules, procedures, rights, and obligations of the GA are outlined in detail in the Grant Agreement. Multiple representatives from each organisation could engage in the GA, with each institution granted one voting right.

The GA convenes four times throughout the project's duration, specifically at M1 (kick-off), M12, M24 and M36. All meetings of the GA shall be chaired by the PC (OpenAIRE), who serves as the liaison between the Consortium and the European Commission. The following decisions are within the purview of the GA:

- Proposals for modifications to the Grant Agreement for approval by the European Commission.
- Alterations to the Project Plan (comprising the Budget and Effort distribution).
- Inclusion of a new BEN, AE, AP into the Consortium, and endorsement of the terms of accession for such a new participant.
- Withdrawal of a BEN, AE, AP from the Consortium, along with endorsement of the conditions of withdrawal.
- Any significant alterations to the project, matters necessitating unanimity, or issues referred by the PSC to a higher level.
- The GA is always the ultimate in-project decision body for Quality Assurance and Risk Management topics.
- Recommendation to the European Commission for a change in the coordination, submission of all or part of the Project, or termination of the Grant Agreement.
- Any other substantial modifications requiring amendments to the Grant Agreement.

WHERE TO FIND THE LIST WITH THE GA MEMBERS?

Teams > OSTrails > WP6 > Flies > Management and Exploitation > General Assembly > [OSTrails_GA](#)

1.2.4. External Advisory Board

The External Advisory Board (EAB) aims at ensuring alignment with international initiatives in the domains of the Plan-Track-Assess building blocks. This will be

accomplished by providing recommendations and feedback on intermediate and final results throughout all crucial stages of project implementation.

The EAB will ensure that project activities reflect cutting-edge knowledge and practices. It will assist the project team in conducting a comprehensive assessment by identifying relevant sources of information and practices. Comprising distinguished experts with global recognition in Open Science, impact evaluation, and cost-benefit analysis, the EAB will offer informed input into conceptual design and methodological advancements, particularly in WP1 to WP3. These high-level experts will provide valuable insights and serve as critical evaluators, challenging conventional thinking on key methodological aspects of the project.

The EAB is expected to consist of approximately four members and will meet twice during the project (M14 and M28), led by OpenAIRE.

1.2.5. Work Packages (WPs) and Work Packages Leaders (WPLs)

OSTrails work plan consists of **six Work Packages (WPs)** to meet the project objectives and realise the results on all technical, outreach and adoption, capacity building, and EOSC flavours (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2. OSTrails Work Packages and their interactions.

WP1 co-develops the Plan-Track-Assess OSTrails-IRA and guides all developments in the project.

WP2 implements the federation within EOSC by aligning existing popular DMP / SKG /FAIR Assessment platforms with formats, ontologies, APIs from WP1, preparing them to support the pilots (WP4) and subsequently to be released in EOSC for a wide use.

WP3 implements the assessment framework by co-developing with experts and discipline communities FAIR tests for different research outputs and evaluating their applicability in a variety of settings via the pilots (WP4). It also co-develops methods and tooling for DMP assessment and investigates user-centred methods for improving the quality of SKGs that enable assessment of research at large.

WP4 oversees the pilots from requirements to implementation and validation, continuously providing feedback towards WP2 and WP3.

WP5 runs in parallel to all project activities and continuously interacts with all WPs supporting dissemination, stakeholder and researcher engagement, and training.

WP6 is dedicated to project management and the assurance of a smooth project flow and timely delivery of results, as well as to the early identification of exploitation paths and the support of a governance for FAIR metrics and compliance within EOSC.

Work Package Leaders (WPLs), listed in **Table 6**, have the responsibility for overseeing the scientific, technical, and administrative aspects within their designated WPs.

Table 6. OSTrails Work Package Leaders.

	WORK PACKAGE NAME	LEAD BENEFICIARY	WP LEADER NAME
WP1	Plan-Track-Assess Pathways architecture design	TU WIEN	Tomasz Miksa tomasz.miksa@tu.wien.ac.at
WP2	Plan-Track-Assess Alignment Implementation	CTU	Marek Suchanek marek.suchanek@fit.cvut.cz
WP3	Assessment tools & services	UPM	Mark Wilkinson mark.wilkinson@upm.es
WP4	Adoption through Pilots	LIFEWATCH	Christos Arvanitidis ceo@lifewatch.eu

WP5	Community Engagement	CLARIN	Francesca Frontini francesca.frontini@ilc.cnr.it
WP6	Management and Exploitation	OpenAIRE	Natalia Manola natalia.manola@openaire.eu

Within their respective WPs, WPLs are tasked with:

- Planning and managing all activities within the WP.
- Developing deliverables and gathering contributions from other participating partners in the respective WPs for both internal and external reporting.
- Ensuring the delivery of high-quality outcomes and adherence to the directives outlined in the Quality Assurance Plan.
- Scheduling regular meetings as necessary.
- Actively participating in project management as members of the PSC, assisting the PC and the TM in coordinating across WPs, and raising relevant issues.
- Preparing technical and status presentations as needed.

1.2.6. Technical & Quality Assurance Board

The Technical and Quality Assurance Board (TQAB), led by the QAM (CITE) with support from the TM (TU Wien), the PC (OpenAIRE) and the DPC/SM (ARC), establishes procedures, structure, and quality indicators to oversee and guarantee the smooth and high-quality achievement of OSTrails' goals and results (**Table 7**). The TQAB formulates the quality assurance process to ensure precise documentation, reporting, and validation of the ongoing work. An internal peer-review mechanism, accompanied by clearly defined criteria, is implemented to ensure that project deliverables adhere to the necessary quality standards and are submitted punctually to the European Commission as official project outcomes. The TQAB convenes annually with an extra meeting held at the project's outset.

Table 7. OSTrails Technical and Quality Assurance Board.

ROLE IN PROJECT	ORGANISATION	NAME
PC	OpenAIRE	Natalia Manola
PM	OpenAIRE	Tassos Stavropoulos
DPC/SC	ARC	Elli Papadopoulou

QAM	CITE	Georgios Papanikos
TM	TU WIEN	Tomasz Miksa

1.3. Communication Channels, Tools, and Processes

The Consortium employs a number of communication channels to ensure effective outreach both internally, within the project, and externally with other projects and interested parties.

1.3.1. Internal Communication and Collaboration

Emails

Day-to-day communication is carried out via emails. All emails should include in the subject line the name of the project, as [OSTrails], based on the naming conventions listed in [Table 9](#).

NOTE: To automatically sort emails into user's Outlook specific folder, it is recommended to create **Rules**:

Select Outlook inbox > Settings > Email > Rules > Add new rule > Select a condition, and what to do with the message based on the condition (e.g. 1. Name: "Rule for sorting OSTrails related emails", 2. Add a condition > Subject includes > "[OSTrails]", 3. Add an action > Move to > Select/Create a folder > OSTrails.

NEED HELP WITH CREATING A RULE?

See the related article on [Microsoft Support](#)

OpenAIRE created and manages all OSTrails related mailing lists ([Table 8](#)). A spreadsheet with recipients is available in the OSTrails Microsoft (see below).

Table 8. List of mailing lists.

LIST	PURPOSE	LEAD BENEFICIARY	LINK
All	For generic communication	OpenAIRE	ostrails-all@openaire.eu
Administration & Finance	For administrative & financial issues inc. effort reporting	OpenAIRE	ostrails-admin@openaire.eu
WP1	For WP1 related communication	TU WIEN	ostrails-wp1@openaire.eu
WP2	For WP2 related communication	CTU	ostrails-wp2@openaire.eu
WP3	For WP3 related communication	UPM	ostrails-wp3@openaire.eu
WP4	For WP4 related communication	LIFEWATCH	ostrails-wp4@openaire.eu
WP5	For WP5 related communication	CLARIN	ostrails-wp5@openaire.eu
WP6	For WP6 related communication	OpenAIRE	ostrails-wp6@openaire.eu
Info	For external communication	OpenAIRE	info-ostrails@openaire.eu
PSC	For Project Steering Committee related communication	OpenAIRE	ostrails-psc@openaire.eu
GA	For General Assembly related communication	OpenAIRE	ostrails-ga@openaire.eu

WHERE TO FIND THE SPREADSHEET WITH THE RECIPIENTS?

Teams > OpenAIRE > OSTrails > WP6 > Files > [OSTrails mailing lists](#)

ADD/REMOVE PEOPLE FROM EMAILING LISTS?

Contact Tassos Stavropoulos (tassos.stavropoulos@openaire.eu)

File Sharing and Storage

OSTrails has established a cloud-based shared collaboration environment, utilising Microsoft Teams services, for file sharing and collaborative document editing. Partner working groups within OSTrails can access the OSTrails TEAMS channel using their email accounts.

While OpenAIRE serves as the owner of the shared OSTrails Teams, files created by any OSTrails member will remain under the ownership of the creator and subject to the conditions of their respective user accounts. Consequently, after creating a file, owners must:

1. Ensure that, in the case of confidential information, the conditions of their account guarantee that the document is accessible only to authorised members, transferring ownership to the PC if necessary.
2. Configure sharing preferences for the files and folders, considering the following:
 - All files related to OSTrails implementation will be generated within OSTrails Teams and visible to all members.
 - Sharing outside the consortium can be done on an individual file or folder basis. If shared externally, it is the responsibility of the file owner to ensure compliance with the Grant and Consortium Agreements, as well as GDPR aspects of the Consortium.
 - Only the project owner has the authority to modify sharing settings.

Consortium members have been granted access to OSTrails Teams. Requests for additional member access should be submitted via email to the PM.

ADD/REMOVE PEOPLE FROM TEAMS?

Contact Tassos Stavropoulos (tassos.stavropoulos@openaire.eu)

NOTE: To access the OSTrails Teams folders, users should follow the steps listed below: **i)** Reach out to the above-mentioned contact person to receive an invitation for the OpenAIRE/OSTrails Teams group, **ii)** Accept the invitation to join: **iii)** If a Teams account already exists, navigate to your profile settings

(top right) in the Teams platform, select OpenAIRE organization and accomplish the process, **iib**) In the absence of a Teams account, please accomplish the process using the Microsoft Teams web app.

In any case, hyperlinks referring to OSTrails Teams folders/files should always be accompanied by the path used to uniquely identify the specific location of the respective folder/file, as follows: e.g. Teams > OpenAIRE > OSTrails > WP5> Files > Branding > Logo > [PNG](#)

Naming Conventions

A unique document identifier to ensure effective version control (see **Table 9**) must reference each document created and stored in the Teams.

Table 9. Naming Conventions.

TYPE	IDENTIFIER
Deliverable document (The identification number as in the DoA)	OSTrails_<Deliverable number>_<Version>
Project presentations	OSTrails_presentation_<Meeting short name>_<date>
Meeting minutes	OSTrails_<WP number>_<Meeting short name>_minutes
Activity Report	OSTrails_Activity_report_<WP&Task number>_<date>
Other project related documents	OSTrails_<WP number>_<document type>
Email Subject	[OSTrails] <Subject>

Templates

On Microsoft Teams, the following templates have been developed and are accessible by all Teams members:

- Deliverable Template
- Presentation Template
- Meeting Agenda Template
- Meeting Minutes Template

WHERE TO FIND THE TEMPLATES?

Teams > OpenAIRE > OSTrails > WP5 > Flies > [Templates](#)

Research Assistance Tool

OSTrails will use Zotero to collect, organise, annotate, cite, and share research. Zotero will act as a central hub for the scientific literature screened and referenced throughout the project.

PROBLEMS IN ACCESSING ZOTERO GROUP?

Contact Tassos Stavropoulos (tassos.stavropoulos@openaire.eu)

Meetings

OSTrails Teams maintains a calendar of meetings organised across the WPs to enhance flexibility in organising participants and enable the efficient management of meetings and events by the Consortium.

Shared Calendar

The OSTrails consortium utilises a shared calendar within Teams, accessible to all BENs, AEs and APs. All meetings, whether conducted online or in person, must be added to the OSTrails Teams Calendar, including a connection link copied into the event description.

Teleconference Tools

The choice of teleconference tool (such as Microsoft Teams, Zoom, Google Meet, etc.) is at the discretion of the meeting organiser.

PROBLEMS IN ACCESSING TEAMS CALENDAR / ORGANIZING A MEETING?

Contact Tassos Stavropoulos tassos.stavropoulos@openaire.eu

Internal Newsletter

Every 4 months, PC sends a debriefing to keep the consortium up to date about important project updates, deliverables status, milestones, WP status information, news, events and project outputs, other action points and announcements.

1.3.2. External Communication

All outputs created by the OSTrails Consortium will be available under the **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license**.

Zenodo Community

OSTrails created and maintain a Zenodo community to collect **all** scientific results and outcomes of outreach, communication and engagement activities of the project.

*VISIT THE **OSTRAILS ZENODO COMMUNITY** [HERE](#)*

Funding Acknowledgement

All OSTrails communication and dissemination materials as well as publications and other outputs must acknowledge EU support by displaying the European emblem and funding statement as well as the EOSC ("supporting EOSC").

Logo

A branding document was created, which describes how the OSTrails project should be visually presented and serves as a blueprint for maintaining visual consistency and coherence in project-related activities.

Figure 3. Project Logo (with tagline).

Figure 4. Project Logo (graph only).

All project documents must incorporate the official project logo designed by WP6. Three versions of the logo are provided in .png or .svg format to fit the layout of the document: one with a tagline, one without and one with a white font (**Figure 3 - Figure 4**).

WHERE TO FIND THE BRANDING DOCUMENT

Teams > OpenAIRE > OSTrails > WP5 > Files > Branding > [OSTrails brand guidelines-2](#)

WHERE TO FIND THE LOGOS?

Teams > OpenAIRE > OSTrails > WP5 > Files > Branding > [Logo](#)

Website

The website of the project is the main point of reference presenting the project, the consortium, the pillars of work, the pilots for adoption of results, linking providing access to all project results and materials. It is further used to announce events and publish news items and blog posts about the progress of the project.

VISIT THE OSTRAILS WEBSITE AT <https://ostrails.eu/>

Social Media Platforms

The handle for the Twitter/X account for the project is: [@OSTrails](#)

OSTrail's LinkedIn can be found [here](#).

EOSC Forum

All EOSC related projects are represented in the EOSC Forum, the stakeholder forum operated and maintained by the EOSC Association to support the EOSC Governance and foster discussion between the projects. OSTrails is represented as shown in **Table 10**.

Table 10. OSTrails representative in the EOSC Forum.

TECHNOLOGY	IMPACT	COMMUNICATIONS AND ENGAGEMENT
Tomasz Miksa, TUWien	Elli Papadopoulou, ARC	Iro Bournazou, OpenAIRE

Events

OSTrails WP5 maintains an events calendar on the ostrail.eu website. All consortium members can populate the corresponding Teams spreadsheet filename with the events they plan to participate, actively or with simple attendance, the events they would need support in organising and/or the events that could be of overall interest by other OSTrails partners. Every time an event is added on the spreadsheet, WP5 leader receives an email and can proceed, where necessary, with updating the website calendar according to the spreadsheet information.

WHERE TO FIND THE EVENTS LIST?

Teams > OpenAIRE > OSTrails > WP5 > Files > Dissemination Activities > [OSTrails Events planning and overview](#)

Recordings

Recording meetings is subject to the consent of participants and may be applicable to GA, PSC, the AB, and any meetings involving external stakeholders, adhering to GDPR regulations.

2. Quality Assurance

2.1. Strategy

In an interdisciplinary and multifaceted project such as OSTrails it is essential that Quality Assurance is designed so that it covers each and every activity of the project and every kind of artifact it will produce. An item of inferior quality not only affects the overall sustainability of the project and the reputation of engaged partners and individuals but may have cascading effects in the progress of the project and its contractual obligations.

The procedures described in this document will address all required activities for the smooth and effective evolution of OSTrails project until its completion. The overall goal is to achieve and maintain (i) high-quality of the work performed and (ii) high-quality of project documentation. However, on the other hand, in a Research and Innovation Action, Quality Assurance has to be subtle, escape any bureaucratic construct that may impose a bottleneck to project activities and fairly distribute the effort to project members adding as little as possible to their work, exploiting their expertise the best way possible.

To satisfy those needs, the following elements form the basis of the Quality Assurance process of OSTrails:

- A **Quality Assurance and Risk Management Team (TQAB)** formed in the beginning of the project, supervises the whole QA process of the project, and suggests:
 - The PSC may modify suggestions of the TQAB regarding quality assurance evaluation results, assignments etc.
 - TQAB may directly report any Quality Assurance or Risk Management issue, directly to the GA for further resolution.
 - The GA is always the ultimate in-project decision body for Quality Assurance and Risk Management topics.
- A quality assurance process is defined for **every type of deliverable** or **other publicly delivered artifact** of the project.
 - The process is presented in this document and may be revised in the project lifetime as needed. Responsible for triggering the revision is the Quality Assurance Manager (QAM).
 - The process depends on the item in question and may be adapted with the intervention of TQAB to fit the special needs of specific items due to their complexity or emergency.
- A **review process** is defined for selected artifact types, mainly of contractual project deliverables and milestones, yet the process may be extended to other types of items. The review process is based around the assignment of a nominated reviewer, a strict timeline for deliberation and review of the item and finally its approval.
 - The reviewer is selected:
 - As being as less related to the artifact creation as possible; however, this may not always be feasible.
 - Based on their expertise.
 - According to their availability.
 - To ensure fairness of sharing reviews among project partners.

- The reviewer may assign deputy or replacement from his/her organization at any time. The replacement must be formally announced.
- The reviewer may kindly ask support from other consortium members for reviewing elements of a deliverable, however the review remains his/her responsibility. This review support must be announced to the item authors/editors/creators and the TQAB.
- TQAB may:
 - Review any item at any point in time, in parallel to its normal QA process.
 - Assign additional reviewers to a deliverable according to the complexity of the item or the availability in each period. Additional reviewers perform such activities on a voluntarily basis.
- Reviewers are not required to edit or contribute to the quality of the item with direct effort; however, this may be welcome by the item authors and/or the project. As such, the Reviewers may directly suggest or perform changes which are left to the item manager for acceptance or rejection.
- Two means of approving an item are selected depending on the nature and significance of the item:
 - **Declarative approval**, where partners need to explicitly declare their acceptance or rejection of an item. This is form of a voting process and a quorum is needed. Unless otherwise mentioned, a reasoning will be required for both acceptance and rejection statements.
 - **Silent approval**, which is the most widely suggested process in OSTrails, where a default action is assumed (e.g. "accepted") unless one of the members of consortium raises an objection. Any objection must be reasoned.
- Once an item is **Rejected** there may be several manners for recovering, which depends on the stage and reason for objection.
 - If a rejection is made based on specific required changes, those may be deliberated with the manager and after fixed the item may go through the process again.
 - A rejection occurring in silent approval may escalate to a declarative approval if no other solution is found after repeated deliberation steps.
 - The order of precedence of instruments in the project for approval of items is as follows:
 - Any WG < PSC < GA (< EC)
- A track of any review process is maintained in OSTrails Project Management platform.

2.2. Responsibilities

In the following the responsibilities of the various stakeholders involved in the QA is summarised.

- The Technical and Quality Assurance Board (TQAB):
 - Presents the overall TQAB plan, including risk assessment.
 - Assigns the organisations for reviewing elements and tentatively may propose reviewer names.
 - Proposes to PSC any Quality Assurance and Risk Management related activity.
 - May introduce ad hoc changes to any item QA process based on complexity or emergency reasons.
 - May directly address the General Assembly and any partner on any Quality Assurance and Risk Management issue (non-overridable by PSC).
 - May review any deliverable and project artifact on a voluntary basis. (non-overridable by PSC).
 - May assign additional reviewers (volunteers) to specific items (non-overridable by PSC).
- The PSC:
 - Completes and disambiguates any TQAB proposal.
 - Approves most TQAB actions (except non-overridable).
 - Assigns or re-assigns reviewers.
 - May modify the review process according to TQAB proposal or other reasons.
 - May escalate a silent approval into declarative approval.
 - May escalate any Quality Assurance or Risk Management issue to the GA.
 - Silently or deliberately approves any project artifact.
- Editor / Lead beneficiary:
 - Coordinates authors, contributors, and other beneficiaries to perform the actions that lead to the completion of the artifact.
 - Triggers the review process that corresponds to the artifact type both in communication and project management platform instruments.
 - Requests any exceptional handling from the QAB reasoning on the specialties of the artifact.
 - Acts on the side of the artifact as correspondent for the entire quality assurance process. Routes reviewers' suggestions to the item co-authors/contributors.
 - May request escalation of an issue via the PSC and subsequently GA.

- Reviewers (& reviewers' deputies):
 - Review an item according to the review process established and provide detailed feedback on quality improvement actions that are needed.
 - May voluntarily contribute to the quality of an artifact with specific editing of the item in question.
 - May invite supplementary volunteer reviewers for specific elements of an artifact, after notifying the TQAB and the Editor.
 - May replace themselves with other members of their organization to confront any expertise or availability issues.
- Authors/Contributors:
 - Author the deliverable under editor's coordination
 - Respond to reviewers' requests by complying or rejecting those with sufficient reasoning.
- WP Leaders:
 - May request exceptional handling of deliverables of their WPs due to specialties in urgency, significance and complexity or prior delays.
- Project Coordinator:
 - May review any project item. The review must be announced to the deliverable editor and follow and augment the normal review process (i.e. on the same timeline). The PC is responsible for resolving any review conflict in case such arise.
- General Assembly:
 - Silently or explicitly approves any project artifact before publication or submission.
 - May override any prior decision taken at PSC or GA.
 - May accept a formerly rejected artifact.
- TM and Community Coordinator:
 - Organise and co-lead the PSC with the coordinator.

2.3. Procedures

In the following section the procedure for Quality Assurance of each item type produced by the project is highlighted.

2.3.1. Deliverables and Milestones

The execution of activities is anticipated to align with the Gantt diagram outlined in the Grant Agreement. Furthermore, tasks reliant on dependencies from preceding activities should commence early, ensuring coordination with tasks utilising their outcomes.

Monthly discussions during the PSC meetings will address task coordination and any required adjustments to execution timelines.

In addition to the task execution timeline, the contractual deadlines are documented in both the deliverables **Table 11** and the milestones **Table 12**. WPLs are responsible for coordinating tasks, including those related to quality control, to ensure the timely completion and review of deliverables. Any potential issues leading to possible delays should be promptly identified and brought to the attention of the PSC for the development of contingency measures.

Table 11. List of Deliverables.

DEL No.	DELIVERABLE NAME	WP No	LEAD BENEFICIARY	TYPE	DISSEMINATION LEVEL	DUE DATE (MONTH)
D1.1	Plan-Track-Assess Pathways	WP1	TU GRAZ	R — Document, report	PU - Public	6
D1.2	FAIRness Reference Model for Digital Objects V1	WP1	UPM	R — Document, report	PU - Public	12
D1.3	FAIRness Reference Model for Digital Objects V2	WP1	UPM	R — Document, report	PU - Public	24
D1.4	OSTrails Interoperability Reference Architecture V1	WP1	TU WIEN	R — Document, report	PU - Public	12
D1.5	OSTrails Interoperability Reference Architecture V2	WP1	TU WIEN	R — Document, report	PU - Public	30

D2.1	Analysis of the OSTrails Interoperability Framework Tools Compliance	WP2	CVUT	R — Document, report	PU - Public	8
D2.2	OSTrails Software and Services V1	WP2	CITE	OTHER	PU - Public	14
D2.3	OSTrails Software and Services V2	WP2	CITE	OTHER	PU - Public	24
D2.4	OSTrails Software and Services V3	WP2	CITE	OTHER	PU - Public	32
D2.5	OSTrails Commons Specifications	WP2	CVUT	R — Document, report	PU - Public	12
D3.1	DMP Evaluation Rubric and Service Specifications	WP3	ARC	R — Document, report	PU - Public	12
D3.2	DMP Evaluation Service	WP3	ARC	OTHER	PU - Public	28
D3.3	Toolbox of Testing Services	WP3	UPM	OTHER	PU - Public	30
D3.4	Disciplinary and Thematic Community based Evaluation Extensions for Compliance Assessment V1	WP3	UOXF	R — Document, report	PU - Public	18
D3.5	Disciplinary and Thematic Community based Evaluation	WP3	UOXF	R — Document, report	PU - Public	30

	Extensions for Compliance Assessment V2						
D3.6	SKG Research Product Quality toolbox	WP3	OpenAIRE	OTHER	PU - Public	34	
D4.1	Pilots Methodology and Operational Processes	WP4	UNIVIE	R — Document, report	PU - Public	8	
D4.2	Horizon Europe Report	WP4	OpenAIRE	R — Document, report	PU - Public	18	
D4.3	Case Studies and Proof of Concept Instances	WP4	LIFEWATCH	OTHER	PU - Public	32	
D4.4	Case Studies Evaluation Report	WP4	LIFEWATCH	R — Document, report	PU - Public	36	
D5.1	Strategy and Status Report for Communication, Engagement Exploitation V1	WP5	CLARIN	R — Document, report	PU - Public	8	
D5.2	"Strategy and Status Report for Communication, Engagement Exploitation V2"	WP5	CLARIN	R — Document, report	PU - Public	36	
D5.3	Training Roadmap, Framework and Delivery of Training Library	WP5	UMINHO	OTHER	PU - Public	12	

	and Competence Centre V1					
D5.4	Training Roadmap, Framework and Delivery of Training Library and Competence Centre V2	WP5	ARC	OTHER	PU - Public	36
D5.5	Good Practices in Training, Supporting DMPs, SKGs, FAIR	WP5	OpenAIRE	R — Document, report	PU - Public	34
D6.1	Data Management Plan	WP6	ARC	R — Document, report	PU - Public	6
D6.2	IPR Management and Handover processes report	WP6	ARC	R — Document, report	C-UE/EU-C - EU Classified	30
D6.3	Synthesis Report	WP6	OpenAIRE	R — Document, report	PU - Public	36
D6.4	Policy Briefing I	WP6	ARC	ETHICS	PU - Public	18
D6.5	Policy Briefing 2	WP6	OpenAIRE	R — Document, report	PU - Public	36

WHERE TO STORE WORKING VERSIONS OF DELIVERABLES?

Teams > OpenAIRE > OSTrails > Deliverables > Files > DX.Y

Table 12. List of Milestones.

No	MILESTONE NAME	WP No	LEAD BENEFICIARY	MEANS OF VERIFICATION	DUE DATE (MONTH)
1	Project Launch	WP6	OpenAIRE	Meeting; Document	1
2	Establishment of outreach & project operations	WP5 WP6	CLARIN	Web site; Social media; Pilots concept template & feedback forms; Project handbook	4
3	Methodology establishment	WP1WP6	OpenAIRE	Plan-Track-Assess pathways Methodology & Glossary Establishment; Advisory board setup	4
4	Interim products establishment for cross-task collaboration	WP5, WP1, WP4	TU WIEN	Document: FAIRness model baseline; Draft OSTrails Interoperability Specs & Architecture; Pilots Refined; Dissemination & Engagement Roadmap	6
5	Preliminary analysis results	Preliminary analysis results	CVUT	Document: Current state analysis against OSTrails-IRA; Methodology to engage HE PIs/data stewards; Draft vocabulary criteria & metrics for the Compliance Assessment Toolkit & DMP Evaluation rubric; Governance of FAIR	9

				Compliance body in EOSC	
6	Preliminary implementation products delivery	WP3, WP2	UPM	Software Release: OSTrails Commons draft; Specs for SKG Research Product Quality toolbox	12
7	Internal methodology and design evaluation landmark	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	OpenAIRE	Meeting: First Advisory Board Meeting	14
8	FAIR-by-design DOs, impact policy and technical brief	WP1	TU WIEN	Document: Foundation on boundary conditions and practices to streamline the implementation of FAIR-by-design DOs and their impact	18
9	DMP Evaluation prototype	WP3	UPM	Software: Prototype DMP Evaluation Service	20
10	Pilots and Fit-for-purpose FAIR establishment	WP4	LIFEWATCH	Software: Prototype DMP Evaluation Service services; Digital artifacts: Completion of initial deployment and preliminary technical results from National & Thematic pilots; Fit-for-purpose FAIR Metrics for different digital objects	24

11	Internal implementation & delivery evaluation landmark	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP6	OpenAIRE	Software release; Meeting: Second Advisory Board Meeting; Prefinal platform releases with FAIRness and DMP assessment embedded in participating SKGs and DMP platforms	28
12	Training, Mentorship and Hackathon reports	WP5	CLARIN	Document: Train-the-trainers bootcamps, Hackathon, Mentorship Programme Report	33
13	Project End	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	OpenAIRE	Project reports	36

WHERE TO STORE WORKING VERSIONS OF MILESTONES?

Teams > OpenAIRE > OSTrails > Milestones and Deliverables > Files > MX

Peer Review Process

This section outlines the quality assurance procedures adopted by OSTrails to ensure the production of high-quality deliverables, essential for maximizing the project's success and impact. Various types of deliverables (e.g. reports, software, DMPs) will be generated. Responsibilities for delivering project milestones and meeting deadlines rest with the WPLs and designated lead beneficiaries. WPLs are tasked with monitoring task progress, ensuring adherence to quality procedures and deadlines. The PC conducts a final check before submission to the EU Participant Portal. OSTrails will implement a peer review process involving two BEN or AE or AP per deliverable, with reviewing organisations suggested by the PC. Ultimately, responsibility for deliverable preparation lies with the Work Packages (WPs) and their assigned editor. The peer review process comprises the following steps listed in **Table 13**.

Table 13. Deliverables/Milestones Peer Review Process.

PRIOR TO DEADLINE	ACTION
At the beginning of the project	The PC will propose two review BENs/AEs/APs for each deliverable/milestone (if in report form) to the TQAB, aiming to balance the review workload. These proposals will be then presented to the PSC. If the WPLs disagree with the proposal, they have four working days to suggest alternatives.
At the beginning of the project	WPLs are tasked with assigning two reviewers for each deliverable/milestone, with the ability to adjust the TQAB's initial proposal if necessary. If feasible, a single reviewer may be assigned, with the PSC informed accordingly with reasoning. The PC notifies individuals about the review process to be conducted.
4 weeks	The editor uploads the review version on OSTrails Teams (Deliverables and Milestones > Files > DX.Y Name of Deliverable / MX Name of Milestone > Folder "For review") and informs the PC and the TQAB. The PC then notifies the reviewers, reminding them of the Deliverable Checklist (see Paragraph 3.3). Reviewers have 10 working days to review the deliverable, preferably using track changes or uploading the revised version in the same folder, while keeping aware the TQAB and the PC, WPL, and authors. Authors subsequently have a week to address comments, finalize the version, and notify the PC, WPL, and reviewers.
2 weeks	The PC must receive the revised version of deliverables at least two weeks before the final deadline, ensuring they are submission ready. Additional review time may be needed depending on the deliverable's complexity, and the PC reserves the right to request further revisions, if necessary, assisted by the TAQB. Once revised, the final version must be moved to the respective folder (Teams > OSTrails > Deliverables and Milestones > Files > DX.Y Name of Deliverable / MX Name of Milestone > Folder "For submission").
0	The PC is responsible for the approval and final submission of the deliverables on the EC portal.

WHERE TO STORE WORKING OR UNDER REVIEW VERSIONS OR DELIVERABLES?

Deliverables Checklist

Deliverables must adhere to the specified rules to maintain a consistent project image. They should be written using the standard format outlined in the provided templates, with particular attention given to table formatting, styles for tables and figure captions, and reference formatting.

Each report is required to feature an executive summary, which should encapsulate the most significant results and conclusions from the report, accompanied by figures or tables as necessary. Executive summaries of public deliverables will be made available on the project website.

Before finalizing their work, editor and reviewers are advised to conduct the following checklist (**Table 14**).

Table 14. OSTrails Deliverables Checklist.

	DELIVERABLE STANDARDS
Compliance with the Description of the action/ Feedback from EC	Structure complies with instructions and needs of EC
	Compliance of deliverables with the Description of the Action and the project / call objectives
	Planned vs. actual timeliness of achievement (milestone) / submission (deliverable)
Quality of content	Accuracy and appropriate referencing where necessary
	Evidence-based
	Meaningful conclusions / output
Clarity of presentation	Structure of information presented is clear, logical, and complete
	Specialized concepts are used only when necessary and they are clearly defined
	Visuals, tables, and graphs enhance the legibility and attractiveness of the reports
Quality of English	Language is clear, and the use of grammar is correct
	The style is coherent

	Punctuation is used correctly
Format	The formatting follows the project template and standards and is suitable for publication (if applicable).
	An executive summary is included for reports
	The report complies with the visual identity requirements and other Horizon Europe requirements (if applicable).
	Document uses project templates
	The document includes an executive summary
	Numbering of pages, figures and tables is correct
	References to figures and tables in the document are consistent
	A table of contents is included with correct page numbering.
	A list of acronyms is provided at the beginning of the document
	Figure definition is sufficient
	Figures and tables can be easily read
	Project Name "OSTrails" is used correctly throughout the document, with the current use of capital letters
	Deliverable Title and number are correct in the front page and header, and match the title and number in the EU portal
	Hyperlinks are not broken and remain active after PDF generation.

2.3.2. Publications

To ensure the interests of all consortium partners are protected, the following procedures have been established for scientific publications produced by the project:

- Before submitting any scientific contribution, partners must upload a draft of the publication to the project's Teams and sent notification to PC at least two weeks prior to submission, applicable to both conferences and scientific journals.
- Partners have one week after notification to object if they believe the publication may negatively affect the protection of results or background, or if it contains confidential information. Objections must be justified.

- If no objections are raised within the specified time frame, the publication is considered approved.

A, non-exhaustive, list of general principles partners should comply with on publication authoring in the context of the work performed in OSTrails are listed below:

- All publications produced within the project framework must adhere to an open access policy.
- Partners must restrict their publication content to the parts they are working on otherwise they should be extremely brief in presenting other's work, providing sufficient references.
- If partners are revealing prototypical work of other partners, the latter ones should be included as coauthors and approve the publication and its contents. The ordering of authors should be decided among partners.
- Partners whose work is shared in the publication with a substantial role in the scientific and technological should be invited as co-authors.

Additionally, all publications benefiting from OSTrails funding must include the official acknowledgment and disclaimer outlined in the Grant Agreement and official Horizon Europe guidelines.

Where to store drafts and final versions of Publications?

Teams > OpenAIRE > OSTrails > WP5 > Files > [Publications](#)

2.3.3. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The grant agreement specifies a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) designed to measure the impact of the action, going beyond task completion and deliverable publication. These KPIs, related to achieving technical objectives and dissemination and engagement, are listed below (**Table 15**) and are regularly discussed in PSC meetings.

Regarding the process of quality assurance for project's KPIs the following occur:

- KPI assignment:
 - The TQAB introduces a KPI assignment list.
 - The team consults WP leaders and Technical Manager.
 - Each KPI is assigned to one individual.
 - The individual person is appointed by the PSC following an initial proposal of the PC.

- Each KPI may be broken down to additional sub KPIs.
 - Each sub KPI is assigned to one individual too.
- For each KPI and sub KPI a reviewer is assigned.
- The TQAB will approve the KPI assignment and review list.
- The KPI assignment process needs to be finalized by M4.
- Project management will track all KPIs assignments in the project management platform after the delivery of the list.
- KPI handling:
 - Each KPI responsible presents an estimated timeline for the KPI indicating major points that the KPI will substantially progress to its final target. The timeline is maintained on the project management platform and activity tickets are added for each internal milestone updating the list of evidence towards meeting the KPI.
 - Each KPI responsible may apply a further breakdown of a KPI.
 - KPI responsible may perform further assignments to individual partners and members of the consortium, assigning specific objectives and target values.
 - In case an objection exists in due time, this will be escalated to the TQAB for resolution.
 - All partners contribute to the KPI updates with activities performed.
 - Any contribution to a KPI shall be followed by a brief description of the contribution, w.r.t. to its timing, sizing and validation means.
 - KPI updates are performed on the Project Management Platform, using platform's tools (i.e. issue comments and target value update).
 - KPI updates by partners are communicated to the KPI responsible both:
 - before the achievement (as an intention to)
 - maximum one (1) week after the achievement.
- KPI observation and reviewing:
 - KPI reviewers validate the progress of KPIs on a periodic basis. The default periodic validation is on a quarterly basis.
 - All project boards (GA, PSC, TQAB, EAB) may review KPIs at any time.
 - In case deviations from expectancies are observed, those shall be communicated to project's decision-making boards, such as the TQAB or escalated to the GA in order for action to be taken.

Table 15. OSTrails KPIs.

MEASURE	BASELINE (M0)	VALUE/M36	INDICATOR OF QUALITY
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K1.1: No. of specs and models from OSTrails-IRA accepted into EIF	0	3	8
K1.2: No. of infrastructures/services adopting elements of OSTrails-IRA	0	8	21
K1.3: No of disciplines adopting/adapting the FAIRness Reference Model	0	4	10
K1.4: No. of fit-for-purpose maDMP templates adopted	1	16	37
K2.1: No. of DO types addressed by DMPs-SKGs-FAIR Assessment platforms	5	7	8
K2.2: No. of interlinked metadata exchanged between SKGs	0	+200K	+500K
K2.3: No. of SKGs adopting model/APIs to enrich with FAIR metrics	0	2	5
K2.4: No. of partner services aligned with OSTrails Commons	0	4	10
K3.1: No. of maFAIRTests, maDMPs created and shared via the OSTrails Commons	0	5	10
K3.2: No. of digital objects assessed	0	+2K	+10K
K3.3: No. of funders / universities adopting/adapting the DMP evaluator & rubric	0	3	10
K3.4: No. of annotated SKGs objects	0	1000	4000
K4.1: No. of professionals trained/mentored	0	20	60
K4.2: No. of service providers engaged in hackathons	0	25	50
K4.3: No. of communities adopting and participating in FAIR Metrics Compliance Governance	0	5	10

2.3.4. Activity Reporting

During the project's lifespan, it's mandatory for all WPLs to submit updates every six months. These updates should outline the conducted activities, budget usage, and specifically, the allocation of person-months dedicated to the project by involved personnel during the specified period. Each member of the consortium must fulfil this requirement by sending the requested information, using a specified template, to the PC (OpenAIRE) via email to the following address: natalia.manola@openaire.eu

Where are the reporting templates stored?

Teams > OpenAIRE > OSTrails > WP5 > Files > [Templates](#)

3. Risk Management

The risk management activities within OSTrails have the objective to avoid or minimise the impact of potentially possible, but unlikely or unforeseen, external or internal events that may affect the likelihood to achieve the targeted OSTrails outcome in scheduled time, required quality and/or foreseen cost.

Based also on the risks outlined in the Grand Agreement, the risk management process is repeated at regular intervals during the project execution towards proactive actions and control of risk factors. OSTrails risk management activities implement mitigation wherever and whenever necessary. For sure, not all events can be foreseen but the considered, here, continuous monitoring shall catch all events that endanger the progress and success of OSTrails or the quality its outcomes.

3.1. OSTrails particularities

OSTrails project is a relative large-scale **Research Project**, with substantial portion of **Information Technology (IT)** elements and as such carries all the specialties and risks of projects of the two kinds. Indicatively, one source¹ states that over 20% of software IT projects completely fail, while among the rest only an approximation of 25% fully accomplishes its achievements. Any project in between is either failing in terms of cost or

¹ Microsoft MSDN MOF Definition Presentations (2002)

time or under-delivering. A later approach² shows that up to 5-15% of systems delivered are totally abandoned while close to their delivery, while about 30% succeed their purposes. The last observation shows that even the term “failure” is not as fixed as one could expect it to be. Research oriented projects have one additional risk factor: walking on boundary of state-of-the-art has an inherent increased failure probability.

The following points provide reasons which expose the common failures of similar projects as compared to, other sector’s project:

- Software and research are abstract entities that may be perceived differently by different recipients which impacts their alignment with project’s course and results.
- A large-scale IT and research project is always dissimilar to other large-scale IT projects in several details, i.e. previous success steps cannot guarantee success in the next project.
- There is no algorithmic roadmap for transforming requirements to software, which implies certain limitations to the success project roadmap establishment.
- The ingredients of the implementation of a research and IT software project cannot be precisely defined before the execution of the project, in order to limit the risk, which becomes even more complex in modern ecosystems with numerous internal and external dependencies, like the ones assumed by the OSTrails.
- Requirements and expectancies of recipients of project outcomes evolve in time as the environment of the project and the understanding of the recipients evolves.
- Research projects include “Inherent Risks” i.e. risks that are outside the control of the process and such may be the infeasibility of an endeavour, which though is significantly reduced in the case of OSTrails project, as it builds on established technologies.

In order to minimise specific risk of similar projects, agile methodologies have emerged, however even those focus on preventing specific failures, assuming others are less impactful for the overall project success.

Another challenge is the quantification of the Assets, the risks, likely-hoods, and impact of a project.

Deviating from risk management practices found in other types of projects, and due to similar reasons with a potential for overall project failure, both the prediction and estimation of risks is hard and usually not quantifiable. Furthermore, combined risk

² IEEE Spectrum Online (2006)

possibilities are harder to resolve and quantify, since risks are often not totally independent among themselves.

In context described up to now, we actually use the term *risk* to label any incident that might occur and in one way or another cause a deviation of OSTrails outcome from its expected one. This deviation can be identified in terms of

- functional deviation of the produced system (e.g. lack of features)
- or non-functional deviation of the produced system (e.g. performance)
- timeline extension
- monetary extension (in terms of cost, not claims)

The impact might span several directions, e.g. financial (direct or indirect), ethical, or legal. Two significant challenges in evaluating a risk, once identified, are:

- A. To translate the impact(s) on a comparative term basis (e.g. monetary impact).
- B. To approximate the likelihood of the occurrence of a risk.

The methodology adopted attempts to simplify the evaluation and the metrics associated with it, so that those can be maintained by non-experts in risk analysis, yielding valuable results in the course of the project.

3.2. Methodology

3.2.1. The Assets

Risk has no cost if it does not jeopardize some kind of “Assets”. These Assets can vary from project to project and can usually translated to monetary terms, although this is not always so straightforward. On the other hand, depending on the interest of the project the impact on the Assets and the recovery / avoidance costs can also be difficult to quantify depending on their nature and the risk. Typically, money and time can be used interchangeably, however this is again not straightforward. For example, increasing the expenditure does not indefinitely reduce time, etc.

That which could be quite feasible to identify in other projects, i.e. their assets, is still complex in OSTrails. There is a magnitude of Assets produced, most of which are hard to quantify in monetary or other equivalent terms. For instance, all partners involved have exploitation plans which are Assets that might be exposed to different risks and might have different characteristics (e.g. quantification). An example could be the academic exploitation of the project, i.e. its capability to support PhDs or thesis, etc.

Understanding that it is pointless to overemphasize these details, the core Risk Analysis and Contingency Plan described here will focus only on **OSTrails direct outputs, such as software, services, content, data etc.**

The “total” value of the Assets will be assumed to be the total value of the project, though this is an oversimplification as damages beyond the value of the project could occur in specific cases.

3.2.2. Risk Analysis

Risk Identification

The first part of the methodology is about labelling the risks that the project is exposed to. The method in OSTrails is that each task and collectively each WP of the project will identify the risks they perceive that the Assets that they are expected to deliver, or contribute to, are exposed to.

The labelling of the risks must identify:

- The **source / problem** of a risk, which can be anything external or internal to the project that behaves outside the margins it is expected to behave. Typically, these margins should be settled by the specifications; however, these are not those that are of interest to our Risk Analysis, but rather the margins on which the Plan of the project has been settled on. Multiple sources logically combined can form one risk.
- The **target / impact** which is always internal to the project. Target can be any element of OSTrails that is affected by a source / problem while the impact is the problem raised in the target, expressed in qualitative and/or quantitative manner.

Those need to be stated in a subject and additional note describing a risk in a short yet narrative manner which makes further analysis feasible.

As initial indicators:

- The probability of the appearance of the risk can also be attached as an initial step.
- The relative impact sizing at the project level may be indicated in coarse terms.

However, those are quite probable to be reconsidered at the analysis stage.

Under the above-mentioned approach, implementation members and task leaders will identify low level risks and their impact, while Work package and management leadership will identify higher level risks.

Risk Evaluation

Based on the findings of Risk Identification, each and every risk identified has to be evaluated.

The **Probability** for a particular risk to be met is the first of the two main metrics of our risk evaluation. Although probability should be ranging from 0 to 1, since there are no formulas to define it nor enough experimental data are there for the majority of the risks, it is not easily quantifiable and other means need to be employed for its approximation.

The **Impact** is the second metric of an identified risk, and it offers the measure of the damage that will be caused to the targeted element in case of appearance of the risk. This is also not easily quantifiable, especially in an absolute form that would allow risks to be compared across the project.

This is a typical case in IT project and the workaround is quite common: probability is estimated by indirect methods such as “expert” opinions, offers, negotiations etc. OSTrails will depend on “expert” opinions that label the risks.

However, OSTrails will not adopt the terms of Impact and Probability but rather the terms of Probability Rank and Impact Rank which are more appropriate (**Table 16**). Probability Rank liberates the analysis from the strict mathematical terms, while Impact Rank allows one to add a degree of freedom and use indirect reference to “absolute” costs of risk appearance.

Table 16. Probability and Impact values.

PROBABILITY RANK		IMPACT RANK	
Description	Value	Description	Value
None	0	Does not essentially affect OSTrails	0
Low	1	Affect OSTrails in missing a secondary objective (e.g. inferior quality of a service or a deliverable)	1
Medium	2	Affects OSTrails in missing a secondary objective (e.g. failure to deliver a service or a deliverable) or has a minor impact on several objectives.	2
High	5	Affects OSTrails in missing multiple significant deliverables or services.	5
Certain	10	The maximum impact that may be considered, potentially affecting partners name	10

Risk Classification

Risk Classification is the main part of risk analysis. Having the value of the Assets that are exposed to the risk, the indicator of likelihood of the risk and the potential impact this will have, one can estimate the importance of the risk which is typically measured by the term **Risk Exposure**. Risk Exposure is mathematically calculated as the product of Probability by Impact; thus, we will not use the same term. Instead, we will use **Risk Exposure Ranking** or **Simply Ranking**, which can be calculated either simply as the product of the two rankings or via a third table which maps the Probability and Impact Rankings to Risk Exposure Rankings.

The methodology expects that all risks are collected under a common terminology (as already adopted), aligned, and homogenised by the TQAB and finally are refined to expose errors in estimations or cascading effects those risks may have.

- Duplicate removal as several actors may be observing the same rising risk.
- Analysis and break down of risk elements into additional ones (i.e. sources, impacts) that may be triggering or cascading effects of a particular risk.
- Homogenization of quantification and terminology across risks. This allows that cross-references among risks can be identified and taken into account.
- Sorting of risks according to the source / problem is the next step, so that the often-occurring ones, with multiple effects, can be grouped in one element with the total Risk Exposure Ranking and multiple targets / impacts.

At this point both considered approaches will be adopted:

- First sort the risks under the Exposure Ranking so that the most serious problems can be identified and selected for mitigation.
- Then sort the risks under their Probability Rank allowing identify the ones most likely to emerge and then investigate the chains they might be triggering.

A third alternative that would involve resolution of cascading effects, could potentially be investigated in simpler ecosystems; however, in OSTrails, the complexity of interdependencies prohibits such an exercise.

The highest-ranking risks under the two approaches, will be the ones identified as system risks and their environment will be described in detail, with regards to:

- Triggering of the risk.
- Impact on a qualitative description.
- Impact on cost / time equivalents.

The list of the highest-ranking lists will be further analysed by project experts to reason on the need to be mitigated with any potential impact on partners' costs and work and shall be presented to the project for further handling.

3.2.3. Risk Control

Planning

The reasoning behind the Risk Analysis is to ultimately allow control of the risks of a project / system. Risk Control is the process that allows one to be continuously aware of, and able to react to, risks surrounding the Project. It is not a “once-off” procedure but a task that must be constantly active. A consistent plan is adopted and is set to be followed by assigned people throughout the duration of the project.

This plan involves:

- Setting responsibilities for managing the plan itself.
- Performing periodical updates of the plan.
- Training on aspects of the plan such as a particular risk’s resolution process etc.
- The process for monitoring risks.
- The process for resolving risks.

Planning also sets the enriched set of information that needs to be gathered and analysed as part of Risk Analysis. For each risk it assumes all the elements mentioned in Risk Analysis elements, yet the need for elaborate description is essential for planning the monitoring and mitigation of a risk.

- A full description of the Risk that includes:
 - Source / Problem.
 - Impact in qualitative terms.
 - Situation under which it might occur, perhaps even in a complex logical combination of events.
 - Linked risks.
- Means to monitor the appearance and evolution of the risk.
- Means to handle the risk upon its appearance.
- Responsible(s) for monitoring the risk and responsible(s) for handling the risk, which might differ.
- A timeline (in months) for periodic (or next) re-evaluation of a risk.

According to the methodology, a single list is constructed containing all the details of a risk analysis that is periodically.

Mitigation

Risk Mitigation may refer to the reduction of the Impact Ranking of a risk, which may be either reduction of the probability to emerge or reduction of the impact it might have on project’s Assets. It must be noted though, that a mitigation strategy does not target the

nullification of a risk's appearance probability or full elimination of the impact the risk might cause, since this might be practically infeasible or of disproportional cost. The overall objective of mitigation is the optimal handling of risks, i.e. balancing resources utilized for prevention with the impact expected.

This means that Risk Mitigation might refer to either or both of handling a risk before it is materialized on the Assets of the project or recovering from the damages caused by a risk.

With regards to Risk Mitigation, there are a number of strategies that are applicable to OSTrails, which are enumerated below:

- Evade the risk by eliminating the probability of its triggering events.
- Evade the risk by eliminating its connection with the project.
- Transfer of the risk impact to another party or entity (e.g. insurance)
- Accept the risk without countermeasures.
- Accept the risk with late reaction (i.e. fix issues after the impact initially occurs).
- Exploit risk's side effects for balancing the impact.

One aspect of Risk Analysis is to identify the proper strategy for each risk.

Monitoring

An effective way of Risk Monitoring is the continuous update of the top-n ranking risks of the project. It not only refers to Risks that may emerge and are not yet handled, but also ones that are under execution of countermeasures either for prevention or for reaction to their impact. It requires systematic update of all the relevant contributions (be it description, estimation, or evaluation) so that the ranked list is well maintained and reasoned. This can be an effort/time-consuming process, which imposes an additional project cost that needs to be incorporated to risk management impact. Fortunately, enough, if applied consistently, periodically and in a differential manner, the procedure becomes quite straightforward and can be supported by non-expert actors in Risk Management, such as the workforce of a Research and Innovation Action, as part of their regular activities.

Monitoring is a multi-pass process that engages all processes of Risk Analysis and Risk Planning. It first triggers the update of the risks' list and then, according to the Risk Classification strategy, the risks that score the top rankings enter the further analysis and planning stage. Newcomers i.e. risks that make it to the top rankings for the first time are also subject to further analysis. Risks departing from the list's top-ranking entries, due to either project's mitigation actions or external factors, are also further analysed for further action planning.

For this purpose, for each risk, the following information is used:

- Current Position in the Top-n ranking.
- Previous Position in the Top-n ranking.
- Risk description.
- Risk status and progress towards resolution (if applicable).

3.3. Procedures & Responsibilities

OSTrails adopts the following Procedures and responsibilities for Risk Control.

3.3.1. Planning

The following are the key elements of the Risk Planning process:

- Risk Planning is performed by TQAB, led by the QA Manager.
- The team periodically, approximately on an **eight (8) month** basis, reconsiders the risk plan for potential updates and announces those to the project. The activity starts early in the lifetime of the project, with an initial list of risk presented as part of this Report. Risk Plan updates are presented to the PMB which may present those to the GA depending on their contents.
- **Continuous update process:** PMB monitors and updates risks list on a regular basis as part of the regular PMB meetings with ad hoc information flows. Project Manager is responsible for indicating new risks to TQAB for further analysis, via QA Manager who is also member of the PMB. TQAB will assign responsible(s) outside TQAB for further risk analysis.
- **Periodic update process:** Risk Analysis is performed on a quarterly basis with the support of PMB and the information provided in structured form in periodic reports.
- Key persons from project's workforce (non TQAB members) are candidates for **monitoring risks** that are under observation. TQAB performs an initial assignment which may be revised by PMB.
- Key persons and their organisations are assigned the execution of **mitigation actions** of selected risks identified for handling. Assignments are performed by TQAB either on a personal or institutional basis. PMB validates the assignments and if needed elevates the decision to GA.
- PMB (and consequently the GA) may exceptionally undertake action on any risk not unreasonably **overriding** TQAB indications and Risk Management processes.

Planning process assumes the following information is maintained per risk (**Table 17**), which is supplied by various stages of Risk Control activities. It also coarsely refers to stages mostly responsible for delivering the relevant information.

Table 17. Risk information gathered.

COLUMN	DESCRIPTION	STAGE
ID	A unique identifier for each risk.	Planning / Monitoring
Observed	The date the risk is observed	Planning / Monitoring
Last Update	The date the last update of the risk was performed	Planning / Monitoring
Reporter	Person / Partner that reports the risk	Planning / Monitoring
Responsible (Monitoring)	The person(s) responsible for the monitoring of the risk	Planning / Monitoring
Responsible (Mitigation)	The person(s) responsible for the mitigating of the risk	Planning / Monitoring
Evaluation Period (Months)	The period that this risk requires re-evaluation, in months.	Planning / Monitoring
WPs	WPs involved in risk.	Planning / Monitoring
Source / Problem	The source/problem of the risk, serving also as a title of the risk	Planning / Monitoring
Impact	The impact of the risk as a short statement	Planning / Monitoring
Description	The full description of the risk in a narrative manner allows the reader to comprehend triggering and cascading effects as well as to evaluate the impact and probability of the risk.	Planning / Monitoring
Mitigation Strategy	General mitigation strategy of the risk among the ones selected for the project: Evade risk (Eliminate source/probability)	Risk Analysis

	<p>Evade risk (Disconnect project)</p> <p>Transfer risk.</p> <p>Accept the risk.</p> <p>Accept risk with late reaction.</p> <p>Accept risk and exploit side effects</p>	
Mitigation	Mitigation strategy for the particular risk, in a narrative manner that allows one to identify proper assignments and timeline for the mitigation.	Risk Analysis
Probability Rank	<p>Probability ranks as presented by methodology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None • Low • Medium • High • Certain 	Risk Analysis
Impact Rank	<p>Impact rank as presented by methodology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None • Low • Medium • High • Certain 	Risk Analysis
Risk Exposure Ranking	Calculated Risk Exposure Ranking (Probability X Impact)	Risk Analysis
Previous Ranking	Risk Exposure Ranking of the risk in the previous evaluation, in order to identify rising or dropping risks.	Monitoring
Status	<p>Status of risk handling:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation • No action • Prevention action • Recovery action • Eliminated 	Planning / Monitoring / Mitigation

Cascading Effects (triggers)	Any links to other risks that may be triggered by this risk in case of materialization.	Risk Analysis
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The data are collected on project’s workspace via an online shared document managed by the TQAB and contributed by all PMB members.

3.3.2. Mitigation

The following are key elements of the Risk Mitigation process and responsibilities.

- Risk Mitigation is handled by appointed persons and their organisations.
- Risk Mitigation assignments may be suggested by TQAB, the PMB holding the decision role.
- Once a risk exceeds a level of Impact Ranking the GA may override any prior decision on risk handling and resort to completely different means for the Mitigation strategy and assignments.
- Mitigation process is monitored on a monthly (PMB meetings) and quarterly (Activity Progress Report) basis. All actions taken on Risk Mitigation shall be reported in the Quarterly Activity Progress Report.
- Partners shall be instructed by PMB and subsequently the GA to engage external (i.e. non project) resources for mitigating risks that may arise for the project Assets due to their organizational, technical or scientific shortcomings.

3.3.3. Monitoring

As stated in Risk Planning section, monitoring is performed in two frequencies, monthly and quarterly. The elements of Risk Monitoring are summarized below:

- Risk monitoring is based around the maintenance of the Risk Monitoring List established in the project. TQAB supervises the update of the list.
- Monthly risk monitoring list update is performed in regular PMB meetings. During the meetings specific risks may be identified for out-of-process handling.
- Quarterly risk monitoring list update is performed along regular activity progress reporting by WPLs, using information gathered from Task Leaders.
- Risk analysis is performed on a quarterly basis unless exceptionally triggered by PMB findings.
- Risks ranking changes (i.e. newly highly ranked risks or dropping ranking risks) are identified by TQAB.

- Assignments of mitigation responsible persons (or organisations) per risk are performed as part of monitoring once risk ranking changes are suggested by TQAB. PMB may override – not unreasonably - any such assignment.
- Assignments of risk monitoring responsible persons are suggested by TQAB. PMB may override – not unreasonably - such assignments.

3.3.4. Residual risk

Residual Risk is risk that remains for project assets, after all risk mitigation measures have been applied. Residual risk mitigation is usually a risk control measure for a higher-level risk management enclosing where the project may be a component of. A common top-level measure for mitigating residual risk is to financially ensure the assets of the project, however this is not a common practice in Research and Innovation Action projects.

In the context of the OSTrails, any residual risk will be mitigated by associated partners with any or both of the two following approaches:

1. Time extension of the project.
2. Effort extension of the project.

NOTE: Any offloading of such planning to individual Partner internal risk management processes is expected yet not analysed in the context of OSTrails Risk Management planning.

3.4. Critical Risks

The significant risks that may arise throughout the project's duration and the corresponding contingency measures to manage them are listed in **Table 18** (for the detailed inventory, see the link below). These risks will be deliberated in all PSC meetings to ensure the timely detection of project issues.

Table 18. OSTrails Critical Risks.

RISK No.	DESCRIPTION	WP No	PROPOSED MITIGATION MEASURES
1	Agreement on "minimal level of FAIRness" cannot be reached in a cross-border/domain	WP1 WP3	Build on existing compliance as minimum FAIRness is reflected by existing Guidelines for different DOs and are adopted in a cross-country context and the common ESFRI

	contexts. Likelihood: low; Severity: low		Clusters FIPs in defining FAIRness for cross-domain.
2	One or more proposed assessments cannot be automated. Likelihood: medium; Severity: low	WP3	OSTrails will touch upon a wide variety of digital objects. Already there are automations for publications and data. If rules are more complex, we create a well-documented manual assessment process.
3	Implementation reveals hidden complexity in alignment of tools, resulting in schedule overruns or insufficient alignment. Likelihood: low; Severity: low	WP2	Proper analysis of the current state in the tools is foreseen in WP2. Following an agile approach and based on the complexity of the proposed OSTrails-IRA the project technical manager will define a detailed release schedule for WP2 and WP3 tooling, adjust as needed and align execution.
4	Insufficient or redundant constructs and resources in OSTrails Commons. Likelihood: low; Severity: high	WP2 WP3	The Commons will be designed driven by the needs of the participating tools to share and will be initially populated by methods and pilots (WP3/4). Encourage good documentation and following best OS practices and consider mechanisms for quality.
5	FAIR Assessors not in OSTrails do not follow proposed API. Likelihood: medium; Severity: medium	WP2 WP3	Emphasise EOSC support for OSTrails; encourage Platform authors to attend the hackathon events; promote project Platforms in lieu of competing platforms. Under all circumstances, ensure that all participating Platforms have adapted to the new IF.
6	Tools and methods developed are not flexible enough to be integrated in existing national and	WP2 WP3 WP4	OSTrails partner services are from the start well embedded in the workflows (national infrastructure, RIs) and have shown they are able to deliver flexible and adaptable services.

	thematic workflows (pilots). Likelihood: medium; Severity: high		Intensify codesign with the pilots and the broader community to reduce as much as possible integration and adoption after the end of the project
7	Delayed OSTrails results. Likelihood: medium; Severity: high	WP1 WP2 WP3 WP6	Technical project leadership will declare problematic topics in collaboration with WP leaders and propose resolutions. If consensus cannot be reached on time, or if there is a dependency on external actors, project will follow the Grant Agreement rules.
8	Conditions are changed for pilots (e.g., goals, funding). Likelihood: low; Severity: high	WP4	Pilots are small and self-sufficient, in a way that they don't influence the overall vision. At M3 pilot partners will detail and refine their pilot case studies to reflect current needs and re-align.
9	Low user engagement. Likelihood: low; Severity: high	WP5	Partners will leverage their networks to engage researchers, data stewards & developers early in the project (WP4), with appropriate mechanisms for user feedback (WP5). Increase outreach via national pilot nodes, Horizon Europe PIs and young researcher networks.
10	Low stakeholder engagement. Likelihood: low; Severity: high	WP6	Partners will leverage their connections and networks to engage stakeholders early in the project. Intensify OpenAIRE and ESFRI RIs approach to members. Provide frequent and good quality policy and technical briefs with key messages to attract users.
11	EOSC Integration problems. Likelihood: low; Severity: medium	WP2 WP3	Monitor effort spent and regularly compare actual/planned achievements, identify deviations, and assure early resolution.

12	KPIs achievement. Likelihood: Low; Severity: Medium	All WPs	Other KPIs that are not impacted could be stressed further
13	Delivery of low-quality outcomes (mainly software components of services). Likelihood: Low; Severity: High	WP2 WP3 WP4	Consortium members have a strong record of successful project completion. Agile methodology adopted along with assessment and evaluation being integral processes of project further mitigate the risk. All partners, especially ones with leading roles engage experienced, senior personnel in such activities. The software services build on top of existing, mature and adopted services.
14	Resources sustainability (post project). Likelihood: Low; Severity: Medium	WP2 WP3 WP4 WP5	The project accepts the risk and tries to find additional sources of resources for mid/long term sustainability of resource, adding up to resources that are already secured by partners, minimizing the extent and impact of the risk.
15	Partner underperforms, defaults, or faces other severe operation issues. Likelihood: Low; Severity: Low	All WPs	All partners have an excellent record of project performance and all partners have collaborated in the past with at least one other partner with excellent result, which makes the risk unlikely to occur. Yet project management sets all the structures for handling such an issue, from identifying it to resolving it at GA level.
16	Lack of a required expertise / competence for the success of the project or tasks. Likelihood: None; Severity: High	All WPs	The choice of participants assures full coverage of the landscape of expertise required in the project. Furthermore, the synthesis covers the potential need to strengthen a sector with contribution from other partners, while liaison activities will be fostering synergies that mitigate such risk.

17	Underestimation of the required effort for delivery of services for research and business cases. Too ambitious workplan. Likelihood: None; Severity: Medium	All WPs	The risk is substantially smaller than other RIA cases as the project relies on existing, mature and adopted services, while a rich mix of competences is present to minimize the risk. Furthermore, the project activates on an ecosystem rich of services to complement its offerings. The project will look for synergies and will focus on maximizing reuse of existing technologies.
18	Poor coordination / underperformance of management structures. Likelihood: None; Severity: Medium	WP6	Management structures of the project are well defined since proposal time and have been tested in series of other proposals. Key personnel engaged is quite experienced and well suited to the task assigned. Project coordinator has executed several, larger and more complex projects and all WP leaders have rich prior experience.

WHERE TO FIND THE DETAILED INVENTORY?

Teams > OpenAIRE > OSTrails > WP6 > Files > Technical and Quality Assurance Board > [QATF.RiskMonitoring](#)

4. Conclusions

The current Handbook details the governance and quality control protocols established to ensure the successful execution of the OSTrails project. Oversight of these procedures falls under the purview of the PC, with assistance provided by the TQAB and the PSC. The Handbook is stored in the OSTrails Teams serving as a living document.